

AN INTEGRATED MICROMECHANICS-MACROMECHANICS MODEL FOR THE PREDICTION OF
THE MECHANICAL PROPERTIES OF WOVEN MATERIALS

Roland HARRY [†] Thierry MASSARD ^{††}

[†] *Laboratoire de Génie Mécanique -
Domaine Universitaire - Université de Bordeaux I
33405 TALENCE - FRANCE*

^{††} *Commissariat à l'Energie Atomique
CESTA - BP 2 - 33114 LE BARP - FRANCE*

ABSTRACT

A model for the prediction of the elastic constants and the strengths of woven fabrics is proposed based on a modified micro-macro analysis of an equivalent cross-ply laminate. This model makes an intensive use of the MIC-MAC programs created by S.W. TSAI. Weaving undulation and specific properties of the basic yarn are taken into account. A simple failure model is also proposed which considers the failure modes observed on this type of composite materials. Results from the model are compared to experimental data of a 4H satin commercially available product. Good agreement is found between the characterization data and the predictions given by the model.

KEYWORDS

fabric , macromechanics , micromechanics , strength, elastic constants

1. INTRODUCTION

Designing with composite materials requires the knowledge of the elastic and failure properties of the basic ply which constitutes the laminate. Due to its simplicity, the unidirectional is the best known material and numerous characterization results can be found

in the literature. On the other hand, woven fabrics, which can be manufactured in many different ways (twill, plain, satin...) are not so widely characterized.

The aim of this work is to predict both the inplane elastic behavior and the failure behavior of woven materials using the characteristics properties of the unidirectional equivalent material (same fiber and matrix) and the type of weaving pattern. This prediction model has been introduced in the analysis software «MIC-MAC» developed by S. W. TSAI[1]. It uses the integrated Micro-Macromechanics analysis previously introduced in this software.

2 . PREDICTION MODEL FOR WOVEN MATERIALS ELASTIC PROPERTIES

Many different authors have been interested in predicting the elastic moduli of woven fabrics, either by numerical approaches with finite elements [2], [3], or by some analytical methods [4], [5].

In our method, we modelize the woven material, considered as linear elastic, by the laminate $[0/90]_s$. This latter is a lay-up of basic equivalent plies whose homogenised characteristics have been calculated from the elastic properties of the equivalent unidirectional (same fiber, same matrix), and from the weaving patterns. When the real material has been manufactured, interlacing has appeared between the warp and fill meshes. We define an interlacing parameter:

$$e_b = (l_f - l_t) / l_f \quad (1)$$

where l_f = fiber length and l_t = cloth length

The type of weaving is characterized by the style number:

n = number of yarns in a period as shown in figure 1.

FIGURE 1 - Style number for a woven fabric

The yarns used in the weaving process consist of many elementary fibers imbedded in the resin. The volume fraction of the fiber in the yarn is quite high (0,7 to 0,75). We call V_C and V_T the volume fraction of the fiber for the warp and the fill. These two constituents are represented by homogenised unidirectional plies whose stiffnesses are modified with e_b , n and V_C (V_T).

2.1 - calculation of the equivalent stiffnesses for the interlaced yarns

Y. CHEVALIER and Y. NOVAMANI [4] show that for one wave, the angle of the yarn α can be calculated by :

$$\alpha = \lambda x / l_0 \tag{2}$$

with λ satisfying $\sin(\lambda/2) = \text{th} [\lambda/2(1-e_b)]$

FIGURE 2 - Angle of yarn

This equation can be solved by a dichotomous method. In most common situations, with $e_b = 0,05$ we find $\lambda = 1,082$ rad (see. Figure 3).

FIGURE 3: Determination of $a=\lambda/2$

The stiffnesses can be expressed as function of α :

$$Q_{11}(\alpha) = U_1 + U_2 \cos 2\alpha + U_3 \cos 4\alpha \tag{3}$$

where U_1 , U_2 and U_3 are the invariants defined in [1].for the plane $(1, z)$ containing α

FIGURE 4 - schematic representation of the yarn

$$\begin{aligned} Q_{12}(\alpha) &= \cos^2\alpha Q_{xz} + \sin^2\alpha Q_{yz} \\ Q_{22}(\alpha) &= Q_{yy} \\ Q_{66}(\alpha) &= \sin^2\alpha Q_{yz} + \cos^2\alpha Q_{ss} \end{aligned} \quad (4)$$

we take:

$$\begin{aligned} Q_{xz}(\alpha) &= Q_{xy} = Q_{yz} \\ Q_{yz}(\alpha) &= \nu_y Q_{yy} \end{aligned} \quad (5)$$

Q' is the stiffness matrix of the unidirectional with a volume fraction of fiber of V_C or V_T It can be written in the fibers axes:

$$Q' = \begin{bmatrix} Q_{xx} & Q_{xy} & 0 \\ Q_{xy} & Q_{yy} & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & Q_{ss} \end{bmatrix} \quad (6)$$

The mean values of the yarn stiffnesses Q_{ij}^{yarn} are then calculated:

$$Q_{ij}^{yarn} = \frac{1}{n} \left[2 \left(\frac{1}{\lambda} \int_{-\lambda/2}^{\lambda/2} Q_{ij}(\alpha) d\alpha \right) + (n-2) Q'_{ij} \right] \quad (7)$$

$$Q_{11}^{yarn} = \frac{1}{n} \left[2 \left(U_1 + \frac{U_2}{\lambda} \sin \lambda + \frac{U_3}{2\lambda} \sin 2\lambda \right) + (n-2) Q_{xx} \right] \quad (8)$$

$$Q_{12}^{\text{yarn}} = \frac{1}{n} \left[2 \left(\frac{1}{2} + \frac{\sin \lambda}{\lambda} \right) Q_{xy} + 2 \left(\frac{1}{2} - \frac{\sin \lambda}{\lambda} \right) v_y Q_{yy} + (n-2) Q_{xy} \right] \quad (9)$$

$$Q_{22}^{\text{yarn}} = Q_{yy} \quad (10)$$

$$Q_{66}^{\text{yarn}} = \frac{1}{n} \left[2 \left(\frac{1}{2} - \frac{\sin \lambda}{\lambda} \right) Q_{xy} + 2 \left(\frac{1}{2} + \frac{\sin \lambda}{\lambda} \right) Q_{ss} + (n-2) Q_{ss} \right] \quad (11)$$

The compliance matrix :

$$S_{\text{yarn}} = (Q_{\text{yarn}})^{-1} \quad (12)$$

allows the calculation of the equivalent moduli of the unidirectional representing the yarn:

$$E_{1\text{yarn}} = 1 / S_{11\text{yarn}} \quad (13)$$

2.2 - predicted elastic characteristics of the woven fabric

The effective elastic characteristics calculated for the yarn are used to predict the elastic constants of the elementary ply of a woven fabric. The fabric is modeled as a cross ply laminate $[0/90]_s$ with the volume fraction driven by the amount of fiber in the yarn

$$V_b = 2 V_f / (V_C + V_T) \quad (14)$$

where V_f is the effective volume fraction of fibers in the fabric.

The micromechanical relations that we use are the same as in [1]. The elastic constants of the fabric are derived from the elastic moduli of the homogenized laminate. The 0 degree orientation is the warp and the 90 degree orientation is the fill. These calculations can be made using the MICMAC software described in [1]. It gives a prediction of the elastic properties as a function of the type of fiber, matrix and weaving pattern.

2.3 - results

Results obtained for different fabrics have been compared to experimental results, or to other analytical or numerical methods.

The table 1 shows the results obtained for a balanced E-glass/epoxy plain ($n=2$) with $V_f=0,5$.

	CHEVALIER [4] numerical	MODEL
E_c GPa	22,2	21,1
E_t GPa	22,2	21,1
E_s GPa	3,1	4
NU	0,13	0,124

TABLE 1

The calculations took into account the characteristics of the unidirectional E-glass/epoxy, with a volume fraction of fibers (for the yarn) of $V_C=V_T=0,75$ and a matrix Young's modulus $E_m = 3.1\text{GPa}$.

FIGURE 5 : sensitivity of modulus to V_f for an E-glass/epoxy fabric

Taking into account the weaving decreases the warp modulus whose value is lower than the one obtained with a straight fiber model. Figure 5 shows this difference for an E-glass/epoxy plain weave fabric.

3 - PREDICTION MODEL FOR WOVEN MATERIAL STRENGTHS.

In the same way as in the prediction model for the elastic constants, the fabric is modeled by an equivalent $[0/90]_s$ symmetric cross-ply laminate the fibers of which are the yarns with a volume fraction V_b . The strength to failure characteristics of the yarn are the same as those of the unidirectional material with a volume fraction V_c for the warp and V_t for the fill. The strengths to failure of the basic ply with an effective volume fraction V_b can be calculated using the micromechanics formula developed by S.W. TSAI in [1].

3.1 - Tension strength

The main difference between the laminated system and the fabric is that failure occurs in one step for the fabric and in two steps for the laminate. In the latter case first ply failure occurs in the 90° ply with matrix cracking and last ply failure in the 0° ply with fiber failure at a significantly higher load. It is necessary to adjust the micromechanics parameters of the fabric model to obtain a fragile failure mode (FPF = LPF). This is achieved by changing the strength of the matrix X_m in the cross ply laminate which simulates the woven material. The ultimate strength σ_{ult} of the laminate is assumed to be the tension strength of the modeled woven fabric X.

3.2 - Other strengths

By introducing different loads in the MICMAC model of the equivalent cross-ply laminated model one can obtain easily the predicted values of the strength parameters of the fabric. Tension load in the 0° direction gives the tension strength in the warp direction X. Compression load in the 0° direction gives the compression strength in the warp direction X'. Tension load in the 90° direction gives the Y (tension strength in the fill direction). Compression load in the 90° direction gives the Y' (compression strength in the fill direction). Shear load in the gives the S (shear strength of the fabric). These values are the basic strengths required in most failure criteria used for the sizing of composite structures. We have compared the results of this model with the characterization data of a balanced fabric G803 from BROCHIER with an epoxy fast curing system [6]. The model used the basic data of the T300/F934 systems given in [1] with a global volume fraction of 60% and a 5 harness satin with a volume fraction in the yarn of 75% (warp and fill). Table 2 shows a comparison between the measured and the predicted characteristics of the fabric.

	Experiment [6]	Prediction
E_c GPa	73,6	74,3
E_t GPa	69,4	74,3
E_s GPa	5,7	4,4
NU	0,05	0,042
X MPa	676	662
X' MPa	not measured	442
Y MPa	656	662
Y' MPa	not measured	442
S MPa	91	90

TABLE 2

Figure 6 shows the strength to failure of this fabric for a tension load at an angle θ of the warp direction. Again the model and the experimental data are in very good agreement.

FIGURE 6: Failure strength in tension function of the direction of testing

4 - CONCLUSION

This prediction model of the mechanical behavior of a woven fabric is derived from the well known and widely used micro computed based MICMAC system. It is a simple but very effective model for the pre-sizing of composite structures made with woven materials. It relieves the designer from costly testings of different types of weaving pattern and volume fraction when choosing a woven material since the only necessary data are the one of the unidirectional material at any volume fraction.

However this predicted model will not replace characterization data when high level of confidence is necessary :

- all the manufacturing parameters cannot be taken into account (i.e. modification in the curing cycle)

- the model gives average values but does not predict the scattering of the data which is quite different between a UD lamina and a woven material. All the specific mode of failure of fabric materials have not been taken into account in this model for simplicity reasons.

5 - REFERENCES

- [1] S. W. TSAI
Composite Design 4th Edition - THINK COMPOSITES- P.O Box 581,
Dayton, OHIO 45419
- [2] F. LENE
Technique d'homogénéisation des composites à renforts tissés
Revue Mécanique Matériaux Electricité, N° 433 ,1990,p. 24-28
- [3] T. HIRAJ, T. SENBA
On the mechanical behavior of fabric-strengthened composites considering
three dimensional cross-linked structure - Proceedings of ICCM3, PARIS,1980
- [4] Y. CHEVALIER, Y. NOVAMANI
Présentation et utilisation d'un code de calcul de prévision (application aux
renforts tissés). - Revue Mécanique Matériaux Electricité, N°433,1990,p.14-23
- [5] TAKASHI ISHIKAWA and TSU-WEI CHOU
Elastic behavior of woven hybrid composites JOURNAL OF COMPOSITE
MATERIALS, Vol 16, 1982, p.2
- [6] M. KARAMA
Caractérisation des stratifiés structuraux à base de fibres de carbone et de résine
époxyde dans le domaine élastique. Approche du comportement visqueux.
Thèse Université de Bordeaux 1, 1987.

6 - AUTHORS BIOGRAPHY

Roland HARRY Doctor Engineer from *Institut National des Sciences Appliquées* in Lyon. Professor at *Institut Universitaire de Technologie* in the Department of Mechanical Engineering since 1967. Since 1980, he has initiated several courses on composite materials with the support of *Aérospatiale* and *SEP* in the Continuing Education Program of *Bordeaux University* and for the *CODEMAC's WinterSchool on Composite Materials*.

Thierry N. MASSARD Doctor Engineer from *Ecole Centrale des Arts et Manufactures*, joined the French Atomic Energy Commission (*CEA*) in 1976. He founded in 1986 the European Branch of *THINK COMPOSITES* a 250 member association for the development of computer based sizing methods for composite materials. He is also Professor at *Ecole Nationale Supérieure des Techniques Avancées* in Paris.

